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NEW PENSION REFORM ACT: A RE-APPRAISAL OF SOME
ISSUES OF CONCERN

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INTRODUCTION

Pension Schemes exist to provide post-retirement benefits to employees. Pension scheme was introduced into Nigeria during the Colonial era to provide old age income and security to British citizens working in the country upon retirement. Nigeria's first ever legislative instrument on Pension matters was the Pension Ordinance of 1951, which has retrospective effect from 1st January, 1946. The National provident fund (NPF) scheme established in 1961 was the first legislation enacted to address pension matters of private organizations. It was followed 18 years later by the Pension Act No. 102 of 1979, as well as the Armed Forces Pension Act No 103 of the same year. The Police and other Government Agencies Pension Scheme was enacted under Pension Act No 75 of 1987, followed by the Local Government pension Edict which culminated into the establishment of the Local government Staff pension Board of 1987. In 1993 the National Social Insurance Trust Fund (NSITF) scheme was established by Decree No. 73 of 1993 to replace the defunct NPF Scheme with effect from 1st July, 1994 to cater for employees in the private sector of the economy against loss of employment income in old age, invalidity or death.

Prior to the PRA 2004, most public organizations operated a Defined Benefit (pay-as-you-go) scheme. Final entitlements were based on length of service and terminal emoluments. The Defined benefit (DB) scheme was funded by Federal government through budgetary allocation, and administered by Pensions Department of the Office of Head of Service of the Federation.

In June 2004, the Federal Government decided to take measures aimed at developing a system that was sustainable and had the capacity to achieve the ultimate goal of providing a stable, predictable and adequate source of retirement income for each worker in the

country. Thus, the pension reform act 2004 (the Act) was signed into law by Mr. president which brought a defined contribution system that was fully funded, privately managed and based on individual accounts for both the public and private sector employees. The Act also established the National Pension Commission as the sole regulator and supervisor on all pension matters in the country.

Pre-reform Experience of Public Sector Schemes

In the last two and a half decades, most pension schemes in the public sector had been poorly funded or unfunded, owing to inadequate budget allocations. Budget releases which seldom came on schedule were far short of due benefits.

This situation had resulted into unprecedented and unsustainable outstanding pension deficits estimated at over N2 trillion before the commencement of the PRA in 2004. The proportion of pension to salaries increased from 16.7% to 30% between 1995 and 1999.

The administration of the scheme was generally weak, inefficient, and non transparent. There was no authenticated list/data base on pensioners, while about 14 documents were required to file pension claims. Also, restrictive and sharp practices in the investment and management of pension fund exacerbated the problem of pension liabilities to the extent that pensioners were dying on verification queues and most of the over 300 parastatals schemes were bankrupt before the new scheme came on board.

As regards the private sector, most employees in the formal establishments and all those engaged in the informal enterprises were not covered by any form of retirement benefit arrangements. Most pension schemes were "resignation" rather than "retirements"

Generally, the pension schemes in Nigeria were largely unregulated, without any standard or supervision and highly diversified before the advent of the PRA 2004. It was against this backdrop that the Federal Government constituted various committees headed by Chief Ajibola Ogunsola and Mr. Fola adeola) at different times to look into the challenges of

pension schemes in Nigeria and proffer solutions. It was the Fola Adeola Committee report that was enacted into the Pension Reform Act (PRA) and came into operation on 1st July, 2004.

Goals of a Pension System and Reform

The primary goals of a pension system should be to provide adequate, affordable, sustainable, and robust retirement income, while seeking to implement welfare-improving schemes in a manner appropriate to the individual country.

An adequate system is one that provides benefits that are sufficient to prevent old-age poverty on a country-specific absolute level in addition to providing a reliable means to smooth lifetime consumption for the vast majority of the population.

An affordable system is one that is within the financing capacity of individuals and the society and does not unduly displace other social or economic imperatives or have untenable fiscal consequences.

A sustainable system is one that is financially sound and can be maintained over a foreseeable horizon under a broad set of reasonable assumptions.

A robust system is one that has the capacity to withstand major shocks, including those coming from economic, demographic and political volatility.

The design of a pension system or its reform must explicitly recognize that pension benefits are claims against future economic output. To fulfill their primary goals, pension systems must contribute to future economic output. Reforms should, therefore, be designed and implemented in a manner that supports growth and development and diminishes possible distortion in capital and labour markets.

Types of Pension Reform Options

Pension Reform options are broadly of two types; parametric and structural/systemic.

Parametric changes, involve adjustments to the parameters of the pension system, such as retirement age, contribution rate, vesting period etc. Robalino, 2005, reported that majority of pension reforms have involved adjustments to the parameters of Defined Benefit (DB) pension system (or Point systems). He noted that between 1995 2005, 18 countries increased retirement age, 57 increased contribution rates, 28 modified benefit formulas, 10 changed vesting periods, and 14 changed the contributory base and/or indexation mechanisms.

He observed that adjustments, however, tend to be ad-hoc or discretionary which creates uncertainty regarding the future evolution of the system and that most often financial problem is the motivation. He concluded that parametric changes can be a stand alone reform as in Jordan or a part of a systemic reform as in latin America and Eastern Europe.

Systemic Reform

Involves a complete shift in the pension systems by a country. For instance a shift from a DB system to a Defined Contributory (DC) scheme of Social Pension or Voluntary Pension scheme. Depending on the level of mix or combination of the various systems, the reform may be a single pillar or multi-pillar. Holzmann & Hinz, 2005, in a World Bank study recommended pension reforms with multi-pillar designs that contain some funded elements as a means of achieving effective old-age protection in a fiscally responsible manner.

The suggested multi-pillar pension system is composed of some combination of five basic elements.

- a) A non contributory or "zero pillar" (in the form of a demogrant or social pension) that provides a minimal level of protection;
- b) A 'first pillar' contributory system that is linked to varying degrees to earnings and seeks to replace some portion of income, such as the

- c) A mandatory 'second pillar that is essentially an individual savings account but can be constructed in a variety of ways, such as the new DC scheme in Nigeria;
- d) voluntary 'third-pillar' arrangements that can take many forms (individual, employer sponsored, DB, DC) but are essentially flexible and discretionary in nature; and
- e) Informal intra-family or intergenerational sources of both financial and non-financial support to the elderly, including access to health care and housing; such as the care for old family members by children and relatives as obtained in Nigeria and other African countries.

Holzmann and Hinz concluded that a system that incorporates as many of these elements as possible, depending on the preferences of individual countries as well as the level and incidence of transaction costs, can through diversification, deliver retirement income more effectively and efficiently.

Statement of Key Principles

Holzmann and Hinz, 2005 also advanced the following principles as necessary conditions for any successful reform.

- i. All pension system should have elements that provide basic income security and poverty alleviation across the full breadth of the income distribution. This suggests that each country should have provisions for a basic pillar, which ensures that people with low life time incomes or who only participate marginally in the formal economy are provided with basic protections in old age.
- ii. If the conditions are right, pre-funding for future pension commitments is advantageous for both economic and political reasons and may, be undertaken for any pillar. Economically, pre-funding requires the commitment of resources the commitment of resources in the current period to improve the future budget constraints of government and may contribute to economic growth and development, as it results in net additions to national savings.

- iii. Politically, pre-funding may better guarantee the capacity of society to fulfill pension commitments because it ensures that pension liabilities are backed by assets protected by legal property rights.
- iv. A mandated or fully funded second pillar (DC) provides a useful benchmark (but not a blueprint) against which the design of a reform should be evaluated. It serves as a reference point for the policy discussion and as a means to evaluate crucial questions about welfare improvement and the capacity to finance the transition from pay-as-you-go to funded regimes.

Dynamics of the Pension Reform Act, 2004

The pension Reform Act (PRA) 2004 was enacted and came into effect in 1st July, 2004. The act established a Defined contributory (DC) Pension Scheme as against the erstwhile Defined Benefits (DB) pension system for all employees of Federal Public Service, Federal Capital Territory (FCT) and Private Sector of Nigeria.

Objectives of the Act

The objectives of the PRA were to;

1. Ensure that every retired worker receives his/her retirement benefits, as and when due;
2. Assist improvident individuals by ensuring that they save in order to cater for their livelihood during old age;
3. Establish a uniform set of rules, regulations and standards for the administration and payments of retirement benefits for the public service of the Federation, Federal Capital Territory and the private Sector.
4. Establish a sustainable pension system that empowers employees to have control over their retirement savings accounts (RSA), promotes labour mobility and minimizes incentives for early retirement;
5. Ensure transparent and efficient management of pension funds; and

6. Promote wider coverage of pension scheme in Nigeria.

Pension coverage in Nigeria had been very low; compared to other developing countries. The coverage was 1.3% In Nigeria, 17% in Cameroun and 60% in Mauritius between 1990 and 1999.

Institutional Framework

Under the new PRA 2004, the major operators of the pension are mainly National Pension Commission (PenCom), pension Fund Administrator (PFA), closed pension fund Administrator (CPFA) and pension Fund custodians (PFC)

- i. National Pension Commission (PenCom): PenCom is the Apex Body of Pension Industry in Nigeria, and was established to regulate, supervise and ensure the effective administration of pension matters. Major functions of the body are to;

Establish standard rules for the management of pension, issues guidelines on investment, approve, license and regulate PFA, PFC and CPFA, carry out public awareness and education on the scheme, manage National Data Bank on pension, promote capacity building and institutional strengthening, receive and investigate complaints against operators and employers, impose sanctions or fines on erring employers, PFA, PFC, or CPFA, and ensure that payment and remittance of contributions are made and beneficiaries of Retirement Savings Accounts (RSA) are paid as and when due.

The PenCom Board is made up of a part-time chairman, Director-General / Chief Executive Officer responsible for day-to-day administration, 4 fulltime commissioners to Head Technical Administration, Finance/Investment and Inspectorate Departments and

7-partime members. The part-time members include, representatives of Head of service of the federation, Federal Ministry of finance, Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Nigeria Labour Congress, Nigeria Union of Pensioners, Nigeria Employers' Consultative Association And Security And Exchange Commission.

- ii. Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs): PFAs are private limited liability companies licensed to manage pension funds under the Act. Their functions are as follows :-

Open Retirement Savings Account (RSA) for each employee with a Personal Identity Number (PIN), invest and manage pension funds and assets in accordance with the provisions of the Act, maintain books of account on all transactions relating to pension funds managed by them, provide regular information on investment strategy, market returns and other performance indicators to the PenCom and employees or beneficiaries of the RSA, provide customer service support to employees; including access to employees account balances and statements on demand, and pay retirement benefits to account holder/beneficiary in accordance with the provisions of the Act.

- iii. Closed Pension Fund Administration (CPFA): Any private organization or public agency with existing self funded and well managed pension scheme, that wishes to manage its own fund is allowed by section 39 of PRA and item 4. 15 of PenCom guidelines to be licensed as CPFA. The CPFA shall have the same responsibilities / functions as PFA and report to PenCom.

- iv. Pension fund custodian (PFC): A PFC must be a bank licensed to hold the pension fund assets on behalf of PFA. The functions of a PFC include the following;

Receive the total contributions remitted by an employer on behalf of a PFA in respect of an employee, notify the PFA within 24 hours of the receipt of the contribution, hold pension funds and assets in safe custody on trust for the employee and beneficiaries of the RSA, on behalf of PFA, settle transactions and undertake activities relating, report to Pencom on matters relating to the assets being held by it on behalf of any PFA, undertake statistical analysis on the investments and returns on investments with respect to pension fund in its custody and provide data/information to the PFA and PenCom, as well as executive in favour of the PFA relevant proxy for the purpose of voting in relation to the investments.

Ligibility: The following categories of employees are exempted from the contributory scheme all existing pensioners are exempted from the scheme. Any employee who at the commencement of the Act is entitled to retirement benefits under any pension scheme existing before the commencement of the new scheme (Act) and is scheduled to retire mandatorily on or before 30" June, 2007.

Also, judges and other categories of employees stated in section 291 of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999- judicial officers or any persons whose pensions have been defined and provided for in the constitution are exempted from the scheme.

All the exempted persons shall continue to derive their retirement under the Defined Benefits Scheme.

Contributions into the Scheme

The monthly contributions for an employee covered by the new scheme are made in the following circumstances relating to his/her monthly emoluments. a.

- a) In the case of public and private sectors including informal enterprises,
 - i. Employees are to contribute minimum of 7.5% of basic salary, housing and transport allowances;
 - ii. Employers are also to contribute 7.5% of basic salary, housing and transport allowances

- b) In the case of the military;
 - i. employees are to contribute minimum of 2.5% of basic salary, housing and transport allowances into the scheme.
 - ii. employers are to contribute minimum of 12.5% on basic salary, housing and transport allowances.

- c) Employees may make additional voluntary contribution if desired, into their retirement savings accounts. The Act provides that, any voluntary contribution that

is not withdrawn within five years is tax free. Employees exempted from the scheme are also entitled to make voluntary contributions.

Also section 9(a) of the PRA 2004 provides that an employer may elect to bear the full burden of the scheme, provided that in such a case, the employer's contribution shall not be less than 15% of the monthly emoluments of the employee.

- d) Employees Life Insurance Policy:- in addition to the specified rate of contribution, every employer is required to maintain life insurance policy in favour of each employee for a minimum of three times the annual total emolument of the employee, section 9(3).
- e) The Act (Section 9(b) provides that the rates of contribution may be reviewed upwards upon agreement between any employer and employee from time to time and the National Pension Commission should be notified of such revision. Monthly contributions and retirement benefits in the PRA 2004 are tax exempt.

Retirement Savings Account (RSA):- The administration of Retirement Savings Account is as follows.

Section 11 (i) of the Act requires every employee to open and maintain a Retirement Savings Account with any licensed pension fund administrator (PFA) of his/her choice and a unique PIN number would be issued by the National Pension Commission (PenCom) in respect of the

RSA. The employee is expected to notify his/her employer of the PFA chosen and the PIN number of the RSA. The PFA will appoint a pension fund custodian to take custody of all contributions/assets remitted to RSAs under its purview. The employer is obliged to deduct and remit the stipulated contributions within seven days of payment of monthly salary/emoluments to the pension fund custodian (PFC) appointed by the employee's PFA. The PFC is under obligation to notify the PFA of contributions remitted, within 24 hours of receipt from the employer. While the PFA shall immediately credit the RSA of the employee from whom the employer had made the payment.

Any employer who fails to remit the contribution within the time prescribed shall, in addition to making the remittance already due, be liable to a penalty to be stipulated by the PenCom provided that the penalty shall not be less than 2 percent of the total contribution that remains unpaid.

Withdrawal From RSA:- upon retirement or attainment of the age of 50 years by the account holder whichever is later, withdrawals/pay-offs from the RSA could be done as follows:

Programmed monthly or quarterly withdrawals calculated on the basis of expected life-span (actuarially computed).

Annuity for life purchased from a life insurance company licensed by National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) with monthly or quarterly payments.

Implications on the Employees

Since individuals own the contributions in the RSA, the account holder/employee on retirement from service is no longer at the mercy of government or employer, and is assured of regular payment of retirement benefits. Other implications are as follows:

Old age income is guaranteed as the scheme is fully funded; through monthly contribution. Employee has up to date information on his Retirement Savings Account (RSA) and prerogative to decide who should be his PFA.

Employees may consult benefits consultants to advise them on the best PFA to engage.

The value of the balance in the RSA and the programmed withdrawals at exit from service are subject to the total amount of accrued rights if any, monthly contributions, accruals on investment and the rate of inflation.

Employees who joined the scheme at age 45 and above may need additional or voluntary contribution beyond the stipulated 15% (employee and employer) to achieve a replacement rate above 50% of terminal salary as pension.

Depending on the level of risk a retired employee could bear; he should utilize a proportion of the amount in his RSA to procure annuity from a licensed insurance company.

Employees should seek more knowledge on investment and pension matters in order to take informed decisions on the management of RSA.

Employees should expect superlative services from PFAs.

There are employment opportunities in the new pension industry.

Implications on Employers

The new pension system may have the following effects on the employers.

Most one man businesses may collapse or shrink to home-consult, as it is mandatory for employers with 5 employees and above to contribute into the scheme.

Employers may incur extra cost in education and logistic support for pension administration.

Total staff cost may increase by about 20% for those without existing pension scheme and death benefits.

All employers are required by PenCom to sign an undertaking to fund the existing scheme and nay shortfall in actuarial deficit within 90 days.

Probation period is no longer a condition for vesting.

Directors and officers will become liable for delay and or noncompliance with the PRA or PenCom guidelines.

In maintaining life insurance policy in favour of each employee as required by section 9(3) of the Act, group life may be preferable as it will be more cost effective than individual life policy.

Granting of loans to employees under the scheme would shift to credit companies or institutions such as car dealers or mortgage banks, but employers may have to give comfort

letters to guaranteed regular payments of certain percentage of the employee's salary to defray the debt owed.

Staff with employer-specific knowledge will be difficult to retain, while staff turn-over may be on the increase as the RSA is portable and employee can change employment as still maintain same account.

Private sector organizations with no existing scheme will not be liable for actuarial deficit or past service liability but may be penalized for not starting by 1st January, 2005.

Need for increase in pension payment following salary increases will only involve existing pensioners and exempted employees.

There will be loanable funds for employers to undertake business expansion.

Effects on the Operators of the Scheme

The effect of the contributory scheme on the operators (PFA, PFC, CPFA and PenCom) may include the following.

Owing to the fact that the scheme is relatively new to Nigeria, the operators will have to invest in capacity building in order to acquire requisite knowledge and skill to drive the scheme.

Investment in information technology (IT) may be high as the scheme is fully IT driven.

PFAs should ensure a good mix of investment opportunities in order to mitigate possible investment and mortality risks.

Stiff competition among PFAs to sign on or register employees will increase as the scheme matures.

PFAs with products like, relatively lower management fee (less than 2%) on RSA, waiver of administrative cost, guaranteed minimum pension especially for low income employees, gratuity for account holders and guaranteed minimum investment returns will have good share of the market.

Implications on the Economy

The Nigerian economy is the ultimate beneficiaries of the new contributory scheme. The pension industry under the new PRA is expected to generate over N900 billion long term loanable funds annually when it becomes fully operational.

The macroeconomic impact of the scheme will be felt in the following areas.

A good proportion of the fund to be generated in the industry will be available for trading in the capital market. Therefore the Nigerian Stock Exchange should be well developed and deep enough to accommodate such funds. The funds would also be available to finance and develop long-term infrastructural projects (oil & gas, electricity, road, water, railway and tourism).

There would be stimulation of growth of small and medium enterprises and transformation of the rural sector.

The enhanced mobilization of savings under the scheme will lead to increase in the percentage of savings to Gross Domestic product

(GDP). Interest rate and cost of fund will drastically fall and lead to development of real sector.

There will be job creation in the low-tech and informal sector. The contribution of the insurance industry to GDP will be enhanced.

Safety Nets in the New Pension Scheme

The importance of safety of the pension fund assets cannot be overemphasized as the success of the pension reform is hinged on the availability of funds to contributors when they retire. Since the pensioner will utilize the fund at the end of his working life, it becomes imperative that adequate measures be taken for its protection. Consequently, there are a number of stringent provisions contained in the Act with the singular objective of protecting the pension fund assets. Some of the measures provided in order to preserve the pension fund assets include:

Separation of PFA and PFC:- while PFA invest the funds the custody of the assets is the responsibility of PFC. The clear delineation of their functions makes it difficult for either to misuse the pension funds assets to the detriment of the account holder.

Pension Fund custodian Guarantee (PFC):- It is mandatory for every PFC to issue a guarantee to the full sum and value of the pension fund and assets held it or to be held by it.

Government Pension Contribution:- Government contribution is a first charge on the consolidation revenue of the federation.

Risk Rating Institutions:- These are institutions that will be responsible for rating the instruments that pension funds will be invested in. the ratings will guide the PFA in their investment activities.

Compliance Officers:- Every PFA is required to employ a compliance officer who will be responsible for ensuring compliance with the provisions pension matters as well as the internal rules and regulations of the particular PFA. They are required to liaise with PenCom and the board of directors of the PFA with regards to the activities of the PFA.

Reporting Requirements for PFAs and PFCs:- In order to keep track of their activities, the licensed operators are required to make regular reports of their activities to PenCom. This will enable PenCom to detect any wrongdoing early.

Statutory Reserve Fund:- Every PFA is required to maintain a statutory reserve fund, which shall be credited annually with 12.5% of the net profit after tax to meet claims.

Sanctions: Clear legal and administrative sanctions have been provided for non-compliance with rules and regulations.

Public disclosure of Information:- PFAs and PFCs are required to disclose their rates on return and publish their audited accounts.

Challenges in the PRA2004

The Pension Reform Act 2004, was one of the most well designed reform agenda of the President Obasanjo Government. The provisions of the Act incorporated adequate measures to guide against old age poverty and ensure that every person receives his retirement benefits and when due after an active working life. However, the following few areas require further developments to make the contributory pension scheme robust, sustainable and effective.

- i. **Disability Pension:-**Albeit; the Act made adequate provisions as regards payment of entitlements to the estate or next-of-kin of an employee who died intestate or was declared missing and not found within one year, no arrangement was made in respect of employees who sustain minor or permanent injury/disability in the course of their duties.
- ii. **Minimum Guaranteed Pension (MGP):-** Section 71(1) of the Act provides that all RSA holders who have contributed for a number of years to a licensed PFA shall be entitled to a guaranteed minimum pension as may be specified from time to time by the PenCom. For effective implementation of this provision, relevant guidelines on the number of years an account holder is expected to have contributed to be qualified for MGP should be stipulated.
- iii. **State and Local Governments Pension Schemes :-** The benefits of the new contributory pension system would be better appreciated when the states and local governments buy into it.

Though, the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, does not permit the Federal Government to legislate for state and local governments on pension matters, in view of the inherent advantages of the new scheme, it would be desirable for the other two levels of government to key into the scheme. Otherwise, employees may have to face multiple regulations on pension when they move from Federal Public employment to state or local government

- iv. National Data Bank: The development and management of a National Data Bank is one of the statutory functions of PenCom. Any Data Bank that can not capture information on state and local governments employer/employees who constitute a large percentage of the Nation's workforce can not be described as national in nature. Besides, for PenCom to perform its oversight functions effectively, there should be adequate funding of the data bank.

Feasible Options for Effective Pension System

The PRA 2004 is a good reform document that deserves the support and commitment of all stakeholders for it to succeed. For the Act to achieve the intended goals of eradicating old age poverty and ensuring the establishment of a robust and effective pension scheme, the following options are advanced.

- i. The PRA 2004 as presently constituted is a 3-pillar pension system since it encapsulated; 1st pillar system by allowing continued management of existing pensioners under defined benefits, 2nd pillar which is the main crux of mandatory defined contribution by employer and employee including the opening of RSA and the 3rd pillar involving the voluntary contribution as stipulated in section 9(5) of the Act. The informal intra- family support for the aged members of a household had always been practiced even before the 1st pension ordinance in 1951. It had been part of Nigerian culture for one to take care of his aged parents. However, in order

to make the Nigerian pension system to be deep and robust, the zero pillar, involving social pension should be fully developed.

The Nigerian social insurance trust fund (NSITF) should be given the statutory obligation to provide social pension to the jobless, the disabled and the old people that have been neglected by their family members and without any means of living. It is the duty of government to provide a framework of social protection for these categories of Nigerians. Thus, a multi-pillar pension system is ideal for Nigeria.

- ii. With the framework provided by the PRA 2004 in place, other challenges such as disability pension and MGP could be addressed through parametric reforms by adjusting the pension system administratively as it matures.
- iii. Government should put in place legal/legislative instruments that would ensure that the reform would be implemented over an infinite horizon (long term) such that it would align with political economy of the country and enjoy the support from subsequent governments.
- iv. Also, necessary framework and good governance should be put in place to ensure that the huge pool of funds generated would be effectively and judiciously invested to develop infrastructures and transform the economy.
- v. The efforts PenCom in driving the pension system is quite commendable. The regulatory body should not relent in enforcing strong business ethics and sanctions of any violators of the act to ensure discipline and sustainable standards in the running of the Scheme.
- vi. The PenCom should organize more awareness seminar to educate the public and all stakeholders.
- vii. As a matter of urgency, PenCom should develop credible National Pension Data Bank to ensure that all stakeholders in both formal and informal sectors are well covered.
- viii. States and Local governments should embrace the scheme to enable the country as a whole derive the best opportunities from it.

- ix. On retirement from active service, the RSA holder should be refunded and his accounted credited with 50% the premium paid of life insurance policy by the employer. This would help to enhance the balance in the account and the retirement benefits available to the retiree.

CONCLUSION

The advent of the Pension Reform Act (PRA) 2004 in the Nigerian pension system was a welcome development, and the efforts of the Federal government in ensuring its effective take off/implementation is quite commendable. For the first time, in the history of Nigerian pension system, the employee/account holder is the main focus and the private sector has been put in the driver's seat to ensure good governance, strong business ethics and effective management of the system. The roles and functions of PFAs and PFCs are pivotal to the success of the new defined contributory scheme. It behooves on them therefore, to play the game by the rules, ensure probity, sincerity, unflinching commitment to the success of the scheme and provision of services with passion to account holders/pensioners in order to guarantee availability of retirement benefits as and when due.

The provision of enabling environment for smooth implementation of the pension system is the responsibility of PenCom and the Federal Government. PenCom should ensure effective monitoring of all players adequate sanction of erring operators and good coverage of all stake-holders. The performance indicators for PenCom should include the degree level of compliance by operators and the percentage coverage of Nigerian work force by the scheme over time, using 30th June, 2004 as the base.

Relevant legal framework should be put in place by the Federal government to ensure political economy and necessary support for the scheme by subsequent governments.

The macroeconomic effects of the saving culture the pension system would engender in the country, will go a long way to revolutionize investment into the real sector, generate employment, reduce poverty and stimulate growth in the economy as a whole.

Consequently, it is appropriate for all hands to be on deck in order to ensure the success and sustainability of the Pension Reform Act (PRA) of 2004.

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